

Analysis of Brain Network Structure under Haptic Motor Learning

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Abstract. Motor learning is not limited to task execution but continues during post-training resting periods, potentially reflecting consolidation processes. While previous studies using fMRI have reported reactivation of task-related activity during resting-state, EEG-based network-level evidence remains limited. In this study, we investigate haptic motor learning using a tracking task under visuomotor rotation, and analyze resting-state EEG recorded before and after training. To capture dynamic brain network changes, we employ a tensor-based representation combined with time-varying graphical lasso. We quantify network reorganization using a metric based on the Frobenius norm of differences in Fisher z-transformed partial correlation matrices. The results show a significant positive correlation between resting-state network change and motor performance improvement. These findings suggest that post-training resting-state network reorganization reflects motor learning consolidation, highlighting the importance of spontaneous brain activity in haptic skill acquisition.

Keywords: Haptic motor learning · EEG · Time-varying graphical lasso

1 Introduction

Motor learning in haptic interaction requires adaptive sensorimotor integration. Recent studies suggest that learning-related processes continue during post-training resting-state, contributing to memory consolidation. Although fMRI studies have shown reactivation of task-related activity during resting-state [2], EEG-based investigations of such processes at the network level remain limited.

This study investigates changes in resting-state brain networks following haptic motor learning using a visuomotor rotation task.

2 Methods

Eleven healthy participants, aged 20-23 years and right-handed were recruited. This experiment was conducted in accordance with the ethical committee of

TUAT (Approval No. 251201-0775). Each subject gave written informed consent. One subject was excluded from the analysis due to poor data quality.

Participants were instructed to perform a visuomotor tracking task, in which they used a joystick with their right hand to track a randomly moving target under a 30° visuomotor rotation. Each of the four task blocks (Task1-4) consisted of ten 30-s trials. There was a 12-minute resting period between Task3 and Task4, which was designated as the post-training resting state (RS2). Motor learning performance was assessed using root mean squared error (RMSE).

EEG signals were recorded throughout the experiment at a sampling rate of 256 Hz from channels related to sensorimotor area. To estimate dynamic functional connectivity, we applied time-varying graphical lasso (TVGL) [1] to multichannel EEG data. Partial correlation matrices Ω_t were obtained and transformed using Fisher’s z-transformation. We computed mean matrices for motor task condition (Z_{MOVE}) and post-training rest condition (Z_{RS2}), and defined brain network change (ΔZ) as:

$$\Delta Z = \|Z_{\text{RS2}} - Z_{\text{MOVE}}\|_F, \quad (1)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm.

3 Results and Discussion

Motor performance significantly improved after training, as evidenced by a reduction in RMSE (Fig. 1), indicating successful motor learning.

PCA of partial correlation matrices estimated by TVGL revealed that the first two principal components discriminated between task and resting conditions (Fig. 2A), suggesting distinct brain network states across conditions.

Furthermore, a positive correlation ($r = 0.74$, $p = 0.015$) was observed between RMSE improvement and ΔZ , representing changes in brain network properties between the resting state (RS2) and the motor task (Fig. 2B). This relationship implies that post-training resting-state network reorganization is associated with motor learning consolidation.

These findings suggest that resting-state EEG dynamics play an active role in stabilizing motor memory. Compared to conventional EEG analyses, the proposed approach captures direct functional connectivity using a dynamic graphical model, highlighting its potential as a sensitive marker of haptic motor learning.

A limitation of this study is the relatively small sample size, which should be addressed in future work.

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Our preliminary results suggest that changes in resting-state brain networks are related to haptic motor learning. However, the relationship between fine motor control of the fingers and underlying functional brain networks remains unclear.

Fig. 1: Learning curve based on RMSE

Fig. 2: (A) PCA of brain network states across conditions. (B) Correlation between network change (ΔZ) and RMSE improvement.

We invite researchers in brain science and cognitive neuroscience to discuss how these network dynamics can be interpreted in terms of neural mechanisms of motor control.

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